

Effect of Vibration-Isolation Measures on AFM Height Measurement

Milan Pavúk ^{a)}, Róbert Hinca, and Vladimír Slugeň

Institute of Nuclear and Physical Engineering, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Ilkovičova 3, 841 04 Bratislava, Slovak Republic.

^{a)} Corresponding author: milan.pavuk@stuba.sk

Abstract. In this study, a comparison is made between two Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) vibration-isolation measures: a passive anti-vibration table and an acoustic isolation cover. The focus was on determining the standard deviation from height measurements taken at a single point on a surface. Based on its magnitude, the effectiveness of specific vibration-suppression measures can be determined. Deactivating the air table on which the microscope is placed resulted in an increase in height standard deviation by a factor of 3.1. The impact of the cover, under our typical measurement conditions, was found to be negligible, falling below the detectable threshold of our measurements.

INTRODUCTION

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) is known for its high sensitivity to changes in sample topography [1], making it ideal for studying nanomaterials [2, 3]. However, this high sensitivity comes with a drawback: susceptibility to vibrations during measurement. Vibrations may originate from various sources, including building vibrations, laboratory equipment, or acoustic waves [4, 5]. They are transmitted to the measurement device and consequently affect the recorded images, often appearing as periodic undulations in the image rows [5, 6]. This reduces the clarity of objects in the image and the accuracy in determining their height. Therefore, various measures are taken to suppress the vibrations, such as placing the microscope on a heavy granite slab atop an anti-vibration table and enclosing it under an acoustic cover. Ideally, this table can utilize an active vibration suppression method, or alternatively, a basic passive one [4]. Additionally, other vibration damping mechanisms for AFM, such as hybrid actuator systems [7, 8], negative stiffness mechanisms [9], advanced feedback control strategies [6], and post-processing techniques for noise suppression [10], have been proposed and realized.

It is easy to illustrate how acoustic vibrations during AFM microscopy impact height measurements: When scanning a surface (ideally flat) without an acoustic cover, and introducing clapping during measurement, it results in a noticeable alteration in the current height profile. Consequently, a height profile is recorded that diverges from reality and this poses a problem. Therefore, measurements are typically conducted with an acoustic cover in place. Another advantage of the acoustic cover is that it prevents air currents, which could also disrupt AFM measurements.

The study aims to measure how different methods of reducing vibrations affect height readings taken with an AFM microscope. Such measurements not only provide insight into their effectiveness but also assist in determining which measures are worth enhancing and investing in.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Anti-vibration testing was conducted using the Dimension Edge™ AFM microscope (Veeco/Bruker, USA) on a pneumatic anti-vibration table from TMC (USA) Series 63. All subsequent equipment was sourced from Bruker. Highly Oriented Pyrolytic Graphite (HOPG) HOPG-12M was chosen for its perfectly smooth and clean surface and secured to the microscope base via vacuum suction. A TESPA-V2 probe with a nominal spring constant of 37 N/m was utilized, as it is our standard for solid sample topography measurements. Scanning was performed in tapping mode in air at 270 kHz cantilever oscillation frequency. The microscope was calibrated using the VGRP-15M test grating, which also served to verify the quality of the probe and ensure correct settings of the scanning parameters. For the sake of completeness, it is worth mentioning that the removable cover of the Dimension Edge™ microscope features a large window in the center, which, for practical reasons, is not filled with sound-insulating material.

The paper uses standard terms for the scanning direction: scanning left-to-right is ‘forward’, right-to-left is ‘backward’. The AFM probe always points with its cantilever free end to the left during scanning.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to capture even subtle deviations in height resulting from changes in anti-vibration measures, an experiment has been devised aimed at obtaining a sufficiently large statistical dataset of height measurements. The primary parameter to be monitored and compared is the standard deviation of height measurement. The experimental concept is straightforward and as follows: the AFM tip will be landed on a flat surface of HOPG, and at a single point on its surface, the height will be measured. This point height measurement will be repeated a sufficient number of times. The sole parameter to be varied in the experiment is the combination of anti-vibration measures between individual measurements. Vibrations from external sources transmitted to the measurement will manifest as fluctuations in height during the measurement process, hence influencing the magnitude of dispersion. The standard deviation (SD) of the height is calculated from the measured height data. As is known, this parameter informs about the extent to which individual height measurements, on average, deviate from the mean. The larger the SD , the greater the dispersion of values (effectively variance), and thus the contribution of vibrations to height measurement. Naturally, height measurement is also affected by random errors, such as thermal noise, for instance. By keeping the scanning parameters constant each time, it is assumed that the intensity of this noise will be relatively uniform.

To ensure reproducibility of the measurements, let them be outlined as follows:

1. The size of the scanned area was set to $0 \times 0 \mu\text{m}^2$. (In the AFM microscope control software, the parameter “scan size” was entered as 0. This theoretically concentrates the size of the scanned area into a single point on the sample surface.)
2. The image resolution was configured to 128×128 pixels, totaling 16,384 repeated height measurements and providing a sufficiently large statistical dataset.
3. The scanning speed was set to 1 pixel per 13 ms, which is a typical scanning speed for routine measurements.
4. Conventionally in AFM microscopy, two height images are recorded: one during the forward probe movement and the other during the backward movement. In this experiment as well, both height images were recorded.
5. Each measurement was repeated once. Thus, a total of 4 images were obtained from 2 measurements for each selected combination of anti-vibration measures.
6. With each change in anti-vibration measures, the tip must be retracted from the sample surface to prevent damage to either the tip or the piezoelectric scanning elements.

Let us start with an example of a single-point height measurement on HOPG and the output from such a measurement. In Fig. 1, raw data from a measurement where the anti-vibration table was activated and the microscope was covered with the acoustic isolation cover is presented. One would typically anticipate observing height fluctuations around the mean value (noise) and perhaps some undulations caused by vibrations. However, rather than that, Fig. 1 reveals a significant height gradient. Take note of the overall height range. The gradient in the image aligns with the direction in which new rows were incrementally added during scanning (perpendicular upwards). The height increase along the gradient is not linear but is represented by an inverted parabola, as determined by least square fitting. The gradient also appears in other images from point height measurements.

To partially elucidate why a gradient occurs in the image of point height measurement (Fig. 1), forward and backward scan images after software leveling of the vertical gradient will be utilized (Fig. 2). The leveling was achieved by aligning the rows of the image according to their average height, a process often referred to as 0th-degree polynomial row leveling. On the left in Fig. 2 is an image recorded as if the probe moved forward, and on the right is an image recorded as if the probe moved backward. In these images, the center is homogeneous, but dark or light lines are present on the left and right sides. Differences between these two images are observed in the colors of the lines. While Fig. 2a has some dark lines on the left edge, Fig. 2b has light ones on the same side. A similar difference is observed on the right edges of the images, but the colors are reversed.

FIGURE 1. AFM single point height measurement on the surface of HOPG with potential probe movement. Unprocessed data from backward scan. Measurement performed with activated anti-vibration table and installed front acoustic cover.

Different colors, thus different heights, on the edges of the images recorded during forward and backward probe movement (Fig. 2) demonstrate that the measured data depend on the scanning direction. This can be explained as follows: It is possible that the probe moved sideways even though the size of the scanned area was set to 0 in the software. At the same time, it is possible that the microscope performs corrections to suppress nonlinearity and hysteresis of the motion of piezoelectric elements, which would also explain the parabolic shape of the height in the direction of the gradient.

FIGURE 2. Forward (a) and backward (b) scan comparison after leveling the vertical gradient. The Fig. 2b is Fig. 1 after leveling. Measurement performed with activated anti-vibration table and installed front acoustic cover.

The distinctive lines, protruding from the height image, disappeared completely after leveling their curvature with a 2nd-degree polynomial (Fig. 3b), although some exhibited only linear dependencies. This adjustment was necessary for subsequent statistical analysis of the height data. It can be viewed as a means of correcting systematic errors in measurement. Of course, the ideal scenario would be if no adjustments had to be made to the data at all.

FIGURE 3. Backward scan from Fig. 1 after leveling the tilt (a) of the scan lines and their bow (b).

The height data from Fig. 3b were used to construct the histogram plotted in Fig. 4. This was done to demonstrate the distribution of height deviations (absolute error) from the mean. Before plotting the histogram, the image data were centered on their average height. The histogram appears to closely follow a normal distribution, as indicated by the high goodness-of-fit ($R^2 = 0.999$) obtained from fitting a Gaussian curve.

FIGURE 4. Histogram of height deviations from the mean obtained by repeated measurements at a single point on the HOPG using the AFM microscope. Measurement performed with activated anti-vibration table and installed front acoustic cover.

For each combination of anti-vibration measures, four images were acquired. Two sets corresponded to regular measurement, while the other two were from repeated measurement. The reason for two images per measurement lies in the scanning process: one image corresponds to the forward scan, while the other corresponds to the backward scan. The standard deviation of pixel height was computed for each scan, and both the *SD* values for individual scans and their averages are presented in Tab. 1. For simplicity, Tab. 1 can be seen as a list of anti-vibration measures, each associated with a certain dispersion of values in height measurement due to vibrations transmitted to the height image during the measurement process.

TABLE 1. Overview of anti-vibration measures and their impact on the standard deviation of AFM height measurements. Forward and Backward Scan columns represent std. deviations in pm obtained from forward and backward scans, respectively.

Measurement Conditions		Regular Meas.		Repeated Meas.		Avg. <i>SD</i> (pm)
Anti-Vibration Table Engaged	Acoustic Cover Deployed	Forward Scan	Backward Scan	Forward Scan	Backward Scan	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	28.59	28.91	28.29	29.00	28.70
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	28.07	27.96	28.05	28.60	28.17
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	84.46	78.16	92.11	98.53	88.32

First, let us examine what happened when the acoustic cover was omitted during measurement (Tab. 1, 2nd row). The average standard deviation decreased slightly from 28.70 pm to 28.17 pm, which translates to a decrease of 1.83%. Note that while the *SD* values in the second row of the table, obtained from specific scans, exhibit minor fluctuations, they consistently remain smaller than the values in the first row when comparing the same scanning direction (forward or backward). Based on the analysis of variance using values from the same columns of the table, it can indeed be concluded that measurements without the acoustic cover exhibit less variability compared to measurements with the cover. This result is, of course, surprising. However, it is important to acknowledge that factors such as establishing a new contact with the sample for each change in the configuration of vibration isolation measures (inaccuracy in setting the same setpoint) or software flattening of image rows may have contributed to the decrease in the standard deviation. Without additional measurements and analyses to assess these influences, it remains uncertain whether the standard deviation value without the cover is truly smaller than that of measurements with the cover.

If a conservative approach were adopted, considering the factors mentioned, it could be said that measurements without the cover and with the cover are in good agreement. Nevertheless, the conclusion remains unchanged: the acoustic cover, under our measurement conditions, has no notable impact on the measurement outcome.

Nevertheless, a visible alteration is apparent upon deactivation of the air table with the acoustic cover in place. The average standard deviation in this configuration of vibration isolation measures increased to 88.32 pm. This denotes a 3.1-fold increase compared to the condition with all vibration isolation measures activated (in comparison to the value of 28.70 pm). Moreover, when the table is deactivated, approximately half (52%) of the 16,384 measured heights deviate significantly from the mean, falling outside the 95% confidence interval of $[-2SD, +2SD]$ observed with the table activated. In other words, in only 48% of the measurements taken with the table deactivated, there was a certain level of similarity or agreement with the measurements taken with the table activated.

Additionally, it is observed that by deactivating the table, the variability in the *SD* of the individual scans increases (see the numbers in the last row of the table). The *SD* values fluctuate by 10.1% relative to their mean. Conversely, with the table activated, they fluctuate by 1.1% when the acoustic cover is deployed and by 1.0% when it is not.

The entire process of comparing vibration-isolation measures based on *SD* would be significantly simplified if we had the capability to perform real repeated measurements of a single point on the surface. On the other hand, the article provides guidance on how to proceed if this option is absent in the AFM microscope control software.

CONCLUSION

Through repeated measurements of a single point on the surface of HOPG by the AFM microscope, the standard deviation of the height was determined, enabling a quantitative comparison of two vibration-isolation measures. Upon deactivating the pneumatic anti-vibration table supporting the microscope, the height standard deviation increased by a factor of 3.1. This pronounced increase distinctly underscores the significant influence of said measure on the precision of AFM measurements. Additionally, it was revealed that in our case, the presence or absence of the front cover of the microscope has a negligible impact on height data in a quiet environment at the given scanning speed.

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